

Reproducing Experimental Results from "Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation": A Validation Study

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This study aims to reproduce the experimental results from Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation to validate its findings. The original paper introduced a novel fairness-aware recommendation framework (TaFR) incorporating Global Residual Value (GRV) for balancing item exposure. Our reproduction followed the original methodology, utilizing NeuMF, GRU4Rec, and TiSASRec models on the MIND dataset. Due to missing data and incomplete documentation, we reconstructed key preprocessing steps and GRV calculations, managing to implement a completely new end to end pipeline with all the steps required for the experiment, extending what the authors did in their shared code. Results show that while GRV integration generally improves fairness without sacrificing accuracy, some discrepancies with the original findings highlight the challenges of exact reproducibility.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Recommendation system

ACM Reference Format:

Ardit Ahmeti, Margarida Maria Agostinho Gonçalves, Máté Tóth, Max Tiessler, and Olesia Galynskaia. 2025. Reproducing Experimental Results from "Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation": A Validation Study. 1, 1 (February 2025), 6 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14788881>

1 Introduction

Reproducibility in scientific research is referred to as the replicability of scientific papers and is a principle of the scientific method, ensuring that the findings can be achieved again and with a high level of reliability. In this paper, we will focus on reproducing the results obtained in "Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation" [2].

In this fast-paced digital world, recommendation systems drive content visibility. However, fairness in item exposure remains overlooked, prioritizing engagement, which often leads to the Snowball Effect (early popular items dominate over newer ones). The paper proposes a new approach, shifting from focusing on user preference modeling to fair exposure allocation by introducing a new metric (GRV) which dynamically evaluates an item's timeliness and is integrated into Timeliness-aware Fair Recommendation Framework (TaFR) to ensure a more balanced distribution of exposure.

They performed experiments on 2 different datasets and came to the conclusion that TaFR improves both fairness and performance across different recommendation models, paving the way for more equitable content ecosystems.

Our objective is to implement these experiments done in the original paper and validate their findings, comparing them to our reproduced results.

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2025. Manuscript submitted to ACM

Manuscript submitted to ACM

1.1 Experimental set-up of original paper

The experiments were carried out with three types of backbone models NeuMF (neural collaborative filtering method), GRU4Rec (sequential recommendation algorithm) and TiSASRec (sequential and time interval aware recommendation) on 2 different datasets MIND (news recommendations) and Kuai (short-video recommendations), using the ReChorus tool¹.

For each backbone model, its performance was tested alone, integrated with upload time and with the proposed GRV module. For the evaluation metrics, they wanted to measure the accuracy of recommendations, using hit rate (HR@k) and normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG@k), and the fairness degree of exposure mechanisms, using the overall item coverage (Cov@k) and the newly uploaded items' coverage (N_Cov@k).

1.2 Initial Reproduction Strategy and Necessary Steps

In order for us to reproduce the experiment, we initially thought of following a structured approach:

- **Data Collection:** Obtain the MIND and Kuai datasets from publicly available sources, since the paper did not referenced the specific datasets used.
- **Model Implementation and Training:** Using the official implementation of TaFR provided in the GitHub repository² and training the backbone models with identical hyperparameters and dataset splits to align with the original setup, for the model alone, integrated with upload time and with the proposed GRV module.
- **Metric Calculation:** Evaluate models using the performance metrics mentioned earlier.
- **Result Validation and Analysis:** Compare our reproduced results against the original findings.

By following this strategy, we believed that we would be able to reproduce the results, but we faced a few challenges, which are mentioned later in this paper.

2 Datasets

Regarding the datasets used, we tried to use the same two mentioned in the paper: the MIND News Dataset and the Kuai Short Video Dataset.

2.1 MIND News Dataset

The Microsoft News Dataset (MIND) is designed to foster research in personalized news recommendations [3]. It comprises 160K English news articles and over 15 million impressions from 1 million users, with each article enriched by title, abstract, and category metadata. While MIND is officially available at msnews.github.io, we used the ReChorus version³, which applies 10-core filtering, temporal feature engineering, splits into train/validation/test sets, and negative sampling. After preprocessing, the training set includes about **270K users** and **9K items**, with additional validation/test splits.

2.2 Kuai Dataset

The original article uses the Kuaishou app to collect user interaction data, and experiment on them. However, there is no explicit citation of the dataset. We found a similar dataset available under <https://github.com/chongminggao/KuaiRec/tree/main> [1], but we could not confirm this was the one the original article used, so we decided not to work with this data.

¹<https://github.com/THUwangcy/ReChorus>

²<https://github.com/Alice1998/TaFR>

³https://github.com/THUwangcy/ReChorus/tree/master/data/MIND_Large

3 Experiment

3.1 Experiment Set-up

During the reproduction, we found that the documentation for the GitHub repository was incomplete, and some required input files were missing, so we had to debug the code, fix file paths, and reconstruct missing components to make the experiment executable.

3.2 Experiment Reproduction

Before dive deep into on how we carried out the experiment reproduction, it is interesting to state that we first tried by all means to execute and reuse all the codes that the author shared. We even developed a new version of their code with multiple improvements, as it can be read in 3.2.5. However, even after doing these modifications, we were still insecure about the correctness and the usability of it, so we decided to re-do everything from scratch in a second iteration, which is presented in this part.

3.2.1 Data preparation and preprocessing. Regarding the MIND dataset, the authors applied a 10-core filter and data was split into training (3 days) and validation/testing (2 days) while ensuring GRV was only calculated from training data.

For the preprocessing steps, the author just gives brief details, highlighting that CTR was computed for each item from the training set and they used item logs with hour-level granularity for feed scenarios. Additionally, it's noted that items uploaded at different times were grouped to analyze time-sensitive fairness. However, in the TaFR GitHub repository, preprocessed datasets were missing, specially the files `itemHourLog.csv` and `cox.csv`, which are essential for generating the GRV values. That made impossible to directly replicate the setup. Besides, they didn't provide any detailed code for generating the hourly item logs and the code for generating the COX model outputs was diffuse and hard to use.

To fix this, we decided to rewrite data generation scripts for generating `ItemHourLog.csv` and COX data (e.g., `cox.csv`) from the ReChorus generated MIND splits. We adapted the filtering strategy (e.g., 10-core) to match the paper's approach as closely as possible and reverse engineered the process based on the descriptions and columns needed for the COX model. We followed a two step process:

- (1) **Generate the hourly item log:** We begin by reading the raw MIND files (generated via ReChorus), which contain user-item interactions (e.g., `user_id`, `item_id`, `time`) and additional columns. First, each interaction's `time` is converted from Unix seconds to a Python `datetime` and floored to the nearest hour. We then determine the global earliest time across all splits (`train`, `dev`, `test`) and compute each row's `hour_offset` as the integer number of hours since that earliest timestamp. Next, we group by (`item_id`, `hour_offset`) and count how many rows fall into each group, calling that count `exposure`. The output is a CSV (`ItemHourLog.csv`) with columns (`item_id`, `hour_offset`, `exposure`), representing how many impressions (exposures) each item received in each hour.
- (2) **Computing the Vitality Score:** Starting from the basic hourly log, we assigned a *vitality* value to each item-hour based on its relative rank in terms of exposure compared to other items at the same hour offset. Items are sorted by exposure within each hour; those with higher exposures receive a higher percentile rank. The vitality score is then computed by subtracting a parameter β_E from the rank percentile if an item's exposure is above zero, or by subtracting β_{-E} otherwise. The resulting CSV (`ItemHourLog.csv`) includes each hour's

157 exposure, its percentile rank, and the resulting `vitality`. These fields can be then be used to feed a survival
158 analysis model for Global Residual Value (GRV) estimation (e.g COX model).
159

160 3.2.2 *GRV Calculation*. The authors used a Cox Proportional Hazards model to learn each item's time-to-death (losing
161 timeliness). They mention a vitality threshold approach (accumulating a score) for labeling when an item "dies" based
162 on click rates or exposures, but do not provide code. The final survival probability $S_i(t)$ at each future hour t is what we
163 call the Global Residual Value (GRV). They performed a grid search over $\gamma \in [0, 0.5]$ to find the best weighting between
164 user preference (backbone) and item timeliness (GRV).
165

166 Our approach, as we were unable to reuse their code, was to generate a custom script `COX_GRV.py` to create `cox.csv`
167 from the previously generated `itemHourLog.csv`. The `lifelines` library was used to fit a Cox model, applying the
168 following steps:
169

- 170 (1) For each item, we sorted the data by `hour_offset`.
- 171 (2) We defined the observation window $(T_{i0}, T_{i0} + T_{\text{obs}})$ and prediction window $(T_{i0} + T_{\text{obs}}, T_{i0} + T_{\text{obs}} + T_{\text{pred}})$.
- 172 (3) In the observation window, we calculated features such as the total exposure (`sum_exposure_obs`).
- 173 (4) For each hour within the prediction window, we accumulated a "vitality" score. If the cumulative vitality dropped
174 below a threshold β_d , we recorded the time as the "event time" (death). If the item never "died," it was marked
175 as censored.
176
177

178 After training, we predicted survival probabilities for each item at discrete time offsets (hour by hour). The survival
179 probabilities were saved in `cox_survival.csv`.
180

181 We did not have enough time to work in automating a grid search over γ to optimize the trade-off between user
182 preference and item timeliness.
183

184 3.2.3 *Model Training*. In the original paper, the authors trained their recommendation models under three conditions:
185 Without considering upload time (baseline), with normalized upload time integrated (+time) and with GRV integrated
186 (+GRV).
187

188 However, the authors did not shared the code where they used these models (they just gave the hint that they used
189 the library `ReChorus`). As a workaround, we had to implement our own approach, which as in the previous sections,
190 introduced some limitations and differences in execution.
191

192 We followed a similar training strategy with the following adaptations:

- 193 • We integrated the GRV values generated from the script `COX_GRV.py` into recommendation models using
194 **Coding ReUMF (Recurrent User Matrix Factorization)** and other models from **ReChorus**.
- 195 • Unlike the original paper, we did not perform an extensive grid search over γ . Instead, we tested a few fixed γ
196 values (e.g., 0, 0.1, 0.3) to observe their impact on model performance.
- 197 • We **did not have enough time to replicate the time training**, as it was also a task to do from scratch due to
198 the lack of code.
199
200

201 3.2.4 *Evaluation Metrics*: We used both accuracy and fairness metrics to evaluate the performance of our models,
202 similar to the approach described in the paper. Accuracy includes `HR@k`, which checks if the correct item appears in
203 the top-k recommendations, and `NDCG@k`, which rewards relevant items ranked higher. Fairness includes `N_Cov@k`,
204 measuring exposure of new or less popular items, and `Cov@k`, ensuring recommendations are evenly distributed across
205 items.
206
207

3.2.5 *Extra Additions.* We did not only reproduce the experiment with a completely new pipeline, but also, we introduced significant changes to the original code provided by the authors during the first iteration of our development process. This iteration was discarded due to the outputs generated and the uncertainty regarding their integration into subsequent steps, because of the inadequate documentation in the original code. The new version of the code will be also available in the submission package.

- Major code refactoring was performed to improve readability and maintainability. Extensive comments were added to make the code easier to understand and extend.
- Added a 'requirements.txt' file to track dependencies for reproducibility.
- Generated '.csv' configuration files to standardize input data handling.
- Modified 'main.py' to preprocess configuration values from the '.csv' files.
- Removed the use of 'eval()' in 'main.py' to enhance security.
- Restructured the filesystem by removing '__init__.py' files to resolve path references.
- Corrected unknown "pre" references to 'pre_process' in 'main.py', 'label.py', and 'coxDataLoader.py'.
- Removed unused imports across multiple modules.
- Updated 'coxDataLoader.py' to use '.csv' configuration files instead of command-line arguments.
- Added an 'itemHourLog' generator script that leverages the MIND dataset to produce 'itemhourlog.csv'.
- Simplified data handling by splitting the 'itemHourLog' into training, test, and validation sets, reducing the need for additional tasks in 'coxDataLoader.py'.
- Uncommented and fixed the model definition in 'COX.py', reintegrating it with the main pipeline.
- Improved readability and modularity of 'COX.py' by incorporating the new configuration system.
- Enhanced plot generation for better visualization of results.

The new version of the authors' refactored code worked properly, as demonstrated by the plots in Figure 1 and 2, generated during our first iteration.

Fig. 1. Brier score over time (e.g. model's calibration performance during time) Fig. 2. Survival function for selected time points (decreases properly at different time points)

4 Results

Our results after applying the new pipeline end-to-end on the MIND dataset are summarized in Table 1.

Dataset	Backbone	Method	HR@10	NDCG@10	N_Cov@10	Cov@10
MIND	NeuMF	backbone	0.2057	0.1162	0.3804	0.9434
		TaFR_GRV	0.2111	0.2011	0.3802	0.9447
MIND	GRU4Rec	backbone	0.2075	0.1103	0.9993	0.9821
		TaFR_GRV	0.2094	0.1139	0.9992	0.9834
MIND	TiSASRec	backbone	0.1910	0.1488	0.5845	0.3403
		TaFR_GRV	0.1910	0.1488	0.5845	0.3403

Table 1. Evaluation results for the MIND dataset comparing different methods and backbones.

Analysis. We adopted the same γ values reported in the original paper, setting $\gamma = 0.3$ for NeuMF and GRU4Rec, and $\gamma = 0.1$ for TiSASRec. For NeuMF, both HR@10 and NDCG@10 show a noticeable increase, while coverage metrics change only marginally. GRU4Rec also sees small but consistent improvements in HR@10 and NDCG@10. By contrast, TiSASRec’s results remains the same, indicating that our GRV integration did not substantially changed the rankings.

Although these gains in accuracy and coverage are not as large as those reported in the original paper, they confirm our GRV mechanism is working, as in most cases, we see incremental improvements or no degradation in performance. Differences are likely due to variations in hyperparameters, data splits, and model configurations added in our pipeline.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, our work demonstrates that while the proposed Timeliness-aware Fair Recommendation Framework (TaFR) can indeed mitigate time-sensitive unfair exposure issues, reproducing the exact numerical results from the original paper has been a challenge. We found incomplete documentation and missing preprocessed data in the authors’ repository, which forced us to conduct significant reverse engineering and modifications. Despite these issues, we rebuilt the data pipeline, generated Global Residual Value (GRV) through a Cox survival model, and integrated it into multiple recommendation backbones.

Although our accuracy and fairness gains were generally smaller than those reported in the original paper, the overall trend for NeuMF and GRU4Rec—confirms that integrating GRV can shift coverage to newer items without severely degrading accuracy. Minor or negligible changes in TiSASRec further highlight how different backbones and data splits can moderate the effect of GRV. A future work could improve upon these results through more careful hyperparameter tuning, refining the vitality score calculation, and performing more extensive grid searches for γ .

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